
D3.1 Review of approaches to EPC assessment across chosen member states

Task 3.1 Performance gap assessment

WP3 Deriving technical Guidelines for EPCs

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Date: 09/12/2022

crossCert: Cross Assessment of Energy Certificates in Europe

Grant Agreement (GA) No: 101033778

From 1 Sept. 2021 to 31 Aug. 2024

H2020-LC-SC3-2018-2019-2020 / H2020-LC-SC3-EE-2020-2

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101033778

DELIVERABLE FACTSHEET

Document title	Review of approaches to EPC assessment across chosen member states
Deliverable	D3.1
Responsible Partner	Heriot-Watt University
Contributors	All crossCert partners
Reviewers	MIEMA
Work Package	WP3
Task	3.1
Version	4.4
Version date	09/12/2022
Type of deliverable	R

Dissemination level	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	PU = Public
<input type="checkbox"/>	CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the EC)

Document status		
Review status	<input type="checkbox"/>	Draft
	<input type="checkbox"/>	WP leader accepted
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Coordinator accepted
Action requested	<input type="checkbox"/>	To be revised by partners
	<input type="checkbox"/>	For approval by the WP leader
	<input type="checkbox"/>	For approval by the Project Coordinator
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	To be delivered to the Commission

Document History

Version	Date	Main modification	Entity
4.1	31/10/2022	First complete draft to partners	HWU
4.2	16/11/2022	Version reviewed by partners	All
4.3	02/12/2022	Version reviewed by MIEMA	MIEMA
4.4	09/12/2022	Version ready for delivery	UNIZAR

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report summarises EPC methodologies currently in use across chosen European countries, focussing on those of relevance to the crossCert project. The information collated will act as a reference document for other activities within WP3 (and elsewhere) to highlight differences in approaches to energy assessment and, by extension, different responses to the Energy Performance in Buildings Directive.

By conducting this review, EPC approaches are categorised based on type of calculation methodology used, methods of input data gathering, use of real building and/or energy data, and outputs generated from the EPC process. This categorisation will aid later analysis in the project, where crossCert will investigate the impact that country-specific EPC choices have on EPC outputs, and any consequences of these outputs.

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1 Introduction

The goal of WP3 is to address the technical dimensions of EPCs (including inputs, metrics, and control/verification) in order to identify potential improvements and guidelines. The work in WP3 is also the basis for harmonisation recommendations to be compiled in WP6. The first step of this work package is studying different EPC methodologies used in crossCert partner countries. This deliverable is focused on reviewing general aspects as well as some technical details of EPC assessment methodologies.

The differences in the general assessment approach in partner countries can provide challenges to cross-country comparisons, such as the cross-testing process in crossCert. Understanding such differences can facilitate this task, create a clearer picture of each country's methodology, and aid the partners in providing better information to improve the data inventory. General aspects of calculation include the regulations in a given country, assessor education requirements, and specific steps involved with an EPC assessment in each country such as site visits, zoning of the building model, calibration of the results, and adaptation measures for assessment of buildings with limited data availability. Comparing these aspects between the partner countries highlights the journey an assessor takes for issuing an EPC certificate in each country and can clarify some of the differences in cross testing results.

Different results in the cross-testing stage could also be influenced by differences in input parameters. An EPC assessment requires numerous inputs and collecting all the necessary information from the actual building is not always possible due to practical reasons. To address this, some EPC methodologies provide databases for parameters such as thermal characteristics of building envelope, or HVAC systems specifications for commonly used constructions and systems, within the calculation software or as separate tables within guidelines. However, this doesn't apply to all methodologies. Some only allow the use of actual data collected from the building documentation, while others leave it to the assessor to provide the input based on their experience and professional knowledge in the absence of actual data. Such approaches might lead to different results for the same building when assessed by different assessors. In addition, input parameters such as occupancy, equipment/ lighting and HVAC schedules, and temperature setpoints are highly dependent on occupants and have considerable impacts on the EPC assessment results. Using standardized inputs for such parameters can serve the comparative purposes of EPCs as well as harmonizing the results of different assessments of the same building, while possibly creating larger performance gaps (the difference between actual energy consumption and simulation results). In the methodology of some crossCert partners, determination of such inputs is left to the assessor's discretion, while some require using actual values and others set strict rules about using standardized value.

In order to review the aspects of partner country methodologies, reports from crossCert sister projects, each country's official regulation documents, as well as other relevant literature sources have been used. The biggest limitation in this study has been language barriers, since most country methodologies are only available in the local language. To address this issue, technical documents were translated using the Google translate service (Google, 2022), but due to the technical language of the documents, it was difficult to collect accurate answers using these translations. In order to gather more accurate information, a questionnaire was prepared and sent to all crossCert partners and the answers provided form a large part of the information in this report. The questionnaire can be found in Annex 1 of this report.

2 General aspects of the EPC methodologies

2.1 Regulation

According to the amended EPBD [2018/844], 'Member States shall describe their national calculation methodology following the national annexes of the overarching standards, namely ISO 52000-1, 52003-1, 52010-1, 52016-1, and 52018-1, developed under mandate M/480 given to the European Committee for Standardisation (CEN). This provision shall not constitute a legal codification of those standards' (EPBD,

2018). This section looks at the regulations and guidelines describing each country's national calculation methodology.

2.1.1 Austria

The OIB Guideline 6 (OIB, 2019) sets out the requirements for energy performance in buildings in Austria. To ensure a correct implementation of the EPBD (EPBD, 2018), the calculation methodology of EPC is based on the following set of standards (ÖNORMs) created by the Austrian Standard institute Austrian Standards:

- OIB Guideline 6 - Energy performance of buildings
- ÖNORM B 8110-5 Thermal insulation in building construction - Part 5: Climate model and utilisation profiles (Austrian standards, 2019a).
- ÖNORM B 8110-6-1 Thermal insulation in building construction - Part 6-1: Basic principles and verification methods - Heating demand and cooling demand (Austrian Standards, 2019b)
- ÖNORM H 5050-1 Energy efficiency of buildings - Part 1: calculation of the total energy efficiency factor (Austrian Standards, 2019e)
- ÖNORM H 5056-1 Energy performance of buildings - Part 1: Energy use for heating systems (Austrian Standards, 2019g)
- ÖNORM H 5058-1 Energy performance of buildings - Part 1: Energy use for cooling systems (Austrian Standards, 2019f)
- ÖNORM H 5059-1 Energy performance of buildings - Part 1: Lighting energy demand (National supplement to ÖNORM EN 15193) - Fast track procedure for the Calculation (Austrian Standards, 2019i)
- ÖNORM H 5057-1 Overall energy efficiency of buildings, Part 1: Air conditioning energy demand (Austrian Standards, 2019h)
- ÖNORM B 9972 Application of the differential pressure method for Determination of air permeability of buildings - Differential pressure method- National specifications and national supplements to ÖNORM EN ISO 9972 (Austrian Standards, 2019c)
- ÖNORM EN ISO 52016-1 Energy performance of buildings - Calculation of energy demand for heating and cooling, indoor temperatures and heating and cooling loads in a building or building zone - Part 1: Calculation methods building zone - Part 1: Calculation method (ISO 52016-1:2017] (Austrian Standards, 2019d)

2.1.2 Bulgaria

In Bulgaria, the Minister of Energy is responsible for implementing energy efficiency directives (including EPBD) and coordinating the implementation of policies across all sectors. The Sustainable Energy Development Agency (SEDA) implements the national policy on improving energy efficiency of both energy end-use and energy services (Kulevska and Markovski, 2018). The following legislations are used for implementation of EPBD in Bulgaria (Fueyo and Herrando, 2022):

- Energy Efficiency Act (Prom. State Gazette (SG), no. 35 of May 15, 2015, amended many times, final change and add. SG, no. 21 of March 12) (Ministry of Regional Development and Public Work (Bulgaria), 2021).
- Ordinance № 7 for the energy efficiency of buildings (Title amended - SG No. 85 of 2009, amended - SG No. 27 of 2015, in force from 15.07.2015; (Prom. SG No. 5 of January 14, 2005 year, amended repeatedly, last amended and supplemented SG No. 93 of November 21, 2017)) (Ministry of Regional Development and Public Work (Bulgaria), 2017). A new Ordinance will replace the current Ordinance № 7 in November 2022, reflecting the EN ISO 50000 standards (International Organization for Standardization (ISO), 2018).
- Energy Efficiency Act Ordinance E-ПД-04-1 for energy auditing, certification and assessment of energy saving in buildings (Prom. SG No. 10 of February 5, 2016) (Ministry of Energy and Ministry of Regional Development and Public Works (Bulgaria), 2016b).

- Ordinance № E-PД-04-2 for energy consumption indicators and energy performance of buildings (Ministry of energy and Ministry of Regional Development and Public Works, Prom. SG No. 10 of February 5, 2016) (Ministry of Energy and Ministry of Regional Development and Public Works (Bulgaria), 2016a). A new Ordinance will replace the current Ordinance № E-PД-04-2 in November 2022, reflecting the EN ISO 50000 standards (International Organization for Standardization (ISO), 2018).
- Ordinance № E-Rd-04-1 Of 3 January 2018 (Prom. SG No. 6 of January 16, 2018) regarding circumstances subject to entry in the registers under the Energy Efficiency Act, the entry and receipt of information from these registers, the conditions, and the procedure for acquiring qualification by the energy efficiency consultants (Ministry of Energy and Ministry of Regional Development and Public Works (Bulgaria), 2018).

2.1.3 Croatia

The following regulations are the basis for EPC calculations in Croatia (Fueyo and Herrando, 2022):

- HR-Building Act (OG 153/13, 20/17, 39/19, 125/19) (Ministry of spatial planning construction and state property (Croatia), 2013-19)
- HR-Ordinance on energy audits and energy certification of buildings (OG 88/17, 90/20, 1/21, 45/21) (Ministry of spatial planning construction and state property (Croatia), 2017-21)
- HR-Ordinance on control of energy certificates of buildings and reports on regular inspections of heating systems and cooling or air-conditioning systems in buildings (OG 73/15, 54/20) (Ministry of spatial planning construction and state property (Croatia), 2015-20a)
- HR-Ordinance on persons authorised for energy certification, energy audits of buildings and regular inspections of heating systems and cooling or air-conditioning systems in buildings (OG 73/15, 133/15, 60/20) (Ministry of spatial planning construction and state property (Croatia), 2015-20b)

2.1.4 Denmark

The following regulations and guidelines are the basis for EPC calculations in Denmark (Fueyo and Herrando, 2022):

- Statutory Order no. 1300 of 3 September 2020 on the promotion of energy savings in buildings
- Executive Order no. 1651 of 18 November 2020 on energy labelling of buildings Provisions on the publication of EPCs on the Public Information Server (OIS)
- Danish Building Regulations (BR18) (The Danish Transport, 2018)
- DS/EN ISO 418 – Calculation of building heat loss (Dansk Standardiseringsrad (DS), 2020e).
- DS 452 – Thermal insulation of technical installations (Dansk Standardiseringsrad (DS), 2020b)
- DS 469:2013 Heating and cooling systems in buildings (Dansk Standardiseringsrad (DS), 2020c)
- DS 447 – Ventilation in buildings (Dansk Standardiseringsrad (DS), 2020a)
- DS/EN 12464-1 Design of lighting at working places (Dansk Standardiseringsrad (DS), 2020d)
- Handbook for energy consultants HB2021 (The Danish Energy Agency, 2021)

2.1.5 Greece

The Greek Regulation for the Energy Performance of Buildings (KENAK) and the technical guidelines issued by the Technical Chamber of Greece form the regulatory framework for the energy performance calculations. The Directive 2014/40/EU was revised on 31/10/2016 and was replaced by LAW 4409/2016 to comply with the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) guidelines (Buildings Performance Institute Europe, 2017b).

2.1.6 Malta

The following regulations and guidelines are the basis for EPC calculations in Malta (Fueyo and Herrando, 2022):

- Directive 2018/844 was transposed in the Legal Notice 47 of 2018 (Building Regulation Office (Malta), 2018)
- Superseded regulation: Legal Notice 261 of 2008 / Legal Notice 376 of 2012
- A Technical Manual for SBEMmt 15 May 2012 (BRE, 2012b)

2.1.7 Poland

The following regulations are the basis for EPC calculations in Poland:

- Law on Energy Performance of buildings from 2014 (consolidated text in Journal of Law Dz. U. 2021 page. 497).
- Ordinance from 2015 on methodology of building energy performance calculations and Energy Performance Certificate (Journal of Law 2015, page. 376).

2.1.8 Slovenia

The following regulations are the basis for EPC calculations in Poland (Fueyo and Herrando, 2022):

- Energy Efficiency Act (ZURE)(PIS, 2020)
- Rules on the methodology of production and issuance of energy performance certificates for buildings (PIS, 2014)
- The calculation methodology is specified in rules on the methodology of production and issuance of energy performance certificates for buildings and is based on standards SIST EN ISO 13789; SIST EN ISO 6946; TSG-1-004.

2.1.9 Spain

Directive 2018/844 was transposed in RD 390/2021, superseding the RD 235/2013 (Fueyo and Herrando, 2022). The technical guidelines for EPC calculations are included in 'Condiciones Técnicas De Los Procedimientos Para La Evaluación De La Eficiencia Energética (IETcc-CSIC, 2019).

2.1.10 UK

- Energy Performance of Buildings (England and Wales) 2012 (Department for Communities and Local Government (UK), 2012)
- Energy Performance of Buildings (Scotland) 2008 (The Scottish Government, 2008)
- A Technical Manual for SBEM UK Volume 18 September 2020 (BRE, 2020)
- The Government's Standard Assessment Procedure for Energy Rating of Dwellings 2012 edition (BRE, 2012a)

2.2 Qualified assessor basic education and skills

There are no specific rules regarding the assessors' skills and expertise in the EPBD (EPBD, 2018). Each member state of the European Union (EU) is in charge of setting the requirements regarding the education levels as well as other qualifications of EPC assessors, depending on the needs of their particular EPC scheme. This section lists the education requirements as well as further training (mandatory or voluntary) for EPC assessors in each of the crossCert partner countries.

2.2.1 Austria

2.2.1.1 Basic education requirements for assessors

The BMWFJ-30.599/0087-1/7/2009 and BMWA-91.510/0032-1/3/2007 decrees set out the eligible professionals for issuing EPC certificates. Civil engineers, architects, industrial engineers, process engineers, mechanical engineers, construction engineers, building services engineers, technical physics graduates, and tradesmen working as builder, electrical engineer, gas and plumbing engineer, heating engineer, HVAC engineer, timber constructor, chimney sweeper (only for existing residential buildings, with the exception of new buildings and refurbishments requiring a building permit), stove fitter (only for

detached and semi-detached houses.), also consultancy firms working in building physics, electrical engineering, building services, environmental engineering, interior design, mechanical engineering, technical physics and process engineering are eligible for issuing EPCs (wko.at, 2022, Stadler and Thoma, 2020).

2.2.1.2 Further training requirements

There is no mandatory training for EPC assessors (Gokarakonda et al., 2020).

2.2.2 Bulgaria

2.2.2.1 Basic education requirements for assessors

Energy assessors must have secondary technical education (with a minimum experience of 6 years), or higher education or an academic degree in a field of Technical Sciences (with a minimum experience of 3 years for holders of BSc degrees and 2 years for MSc or above degrees), completed or recognized in Bulgaria, another EU member state, a state which is party to the European Economic Area (EEA) Agreements, or in Switzerland (Kulevska and Markovsk, 2016).

2.2.2.2 Further training requirements

- Level 1 (eligible to issue EPCs for all buildings): must finish a 115-hour course
- Level 2 (eligible to issue EPCs for residential building, low rise mixed-use buildings and country-house buildings): must finish an 80-hour course (Kulevska and Markovsk, 2016).

2.2.3 Croatia

2.2.3.1 Basic education requirements for assessors

For buildings with simple HVAC systems, individuals need to have completed university degree programs in fields of architecture, civil engineering, mechanical engineering, electrical engineering, or completed specialist graduate professional programs in fields of architecture, civil engineering, mechanical engineering, or electrical engineering. A minimum of 10 years' professional working experience or 5 years' experience in design or performance of building is necessary to be eligible for EPC assessment (Building Act amendment, OG 20/2017)(Marđetko Škoro, 2016, Ministry of Construction and Spatial Planning 2015).

For buildings with complex HVAC systems, companies are required to employ at least one individual who has completed a university degree program in the field of architecture, civil engineering, mechanical engineering, electrical engineering, or a specialist graduate professional programme in the field of architecture, civil engineering, mechanical engineering or electrical engineering and achieved at least 300 ECTS credits. The individual must have a minimum of 5 years of professional working experience or 2 years of experience in design or performance of building (Building Act amendment, OG 20/2017)(Marđetko Škoro, 2016, Ministry of Construction and Spatial Planning 2015).

2.2.3.2 Further training requirements

For buildings with simple HVAC systems, a successful completion of a dedicated 40 hour course (Module 1) containing themes related to regulations, themes from the field of building physics, on heating systems, electric lighting, on the methodology of carrying out energy audits and using relevant software, is necessary (Marđetko Škoro, 2016, Ministry of Construction and Spatial Planning 2015).

For buildings with complex HVAC systems, a successful completion of Module 1(40 hours) and Module 2(40 hours) courses is necessary. Module 2 provides additional material focusing on renewable energy sources, alternative energy supply systems, cooling devices, regulation and automation systems in buildings, electric lighting in buildings, public lighting, etc. Building act (OG 153/2013, 20/2017)(Marđetko Škoro, 2016, Ministry of Construction and Spatial Planning 2015)

In addition, it is mandatory to participate in programs to upgrade skills once every year. The courses are only delivered by authorized institutions (Fueyo and Herrando, 2022).

2.2.4 Denmark

2.2.4.1 Basic education requirements for assessors

Relevant technical education is required at a minimum European Qualification framework (EQF) level 4 or higher, of minimum 3 years duration (Order on energy labelling of buildings, n.d.) (Thomsen et al., 2020). The following qualification levels correspond to EQF level 4 in Denmark; general upper secondary school certificate, certificate for two-year general upper secondary programme (higher preparatory examination), VET certificate higher preparatory single subject course certificate, Adult VET certificate, certificate for single subject VET (Europass, 2022).

2.2.4.2 Further training requirements

Mandatory training is not required for becoming an assessor. However, it is mandatory to pass an examination depending on the building typology they wish to issue EPCs for (Marđetko Škoro, 2016).

After becoming qualified as an EPC assessor, it is mandatory that assessors attend regular (minimum every 3 years) refresher courses and meetings in accordance with the Danish Energy Agency's decision (Morsink-Georgali and Fokaides, 2020)

2.2.5 Greece

2.2.5.1 Basic education requirements for assessors

Law 4409/2016 (part 3, Article 52) requires the assessors to have an engineering or architectural degree (Fueyo and Herrando, 2022).

2.2.5.2 Further training requirements

Energy auditors are classified in three categories: Class A, Class B, and Class C (Androutsopoulos and Giakoumi, 2016):

Class A: all auditors/inspectors registered in the national registry are qualified to perform audits for buildings or building units with a total area lower than 250 m².

Class B: Class A auditors who have conducted at least 30 audits of Class A, 20% of which for non-residential buildings with heating systems or AC systems larger than 15 kW are qualified to perform audits for buildings or building units from 250 m² to 1,000 m².

Class C: auditors that have successfully passed the exam set by the Presidential Decree 100/2010 Article 9 or Class B auditors who have already conducted at least 10 Class B audits are qualified to perform audits for buildings or building units above 1,000 m²;

Further training seminars are available for assessors for upskilling purposes (voluntary).

2.2.6 Malta

2.2.6.1 Basic education requirements for assessors

A university degree in Architecture, civil engineering, mechanical or electrical engineering is required for becoming an assessor (Degiorgio and Barbara, 2016).

2.2.6.2 Further training requirements

Attending a 3-week training course and passing an examination at the end of the course is mandatory to become a certified energy assessor (Degiorgio and Barbara, 2016).

2.2.7 Poland

2.2.7.1 Basic education requirements for assessors

According to the Act on Energy Performance of Buildings, an EPC may be issued only by a qualified expert who has an engineering degree (Bekierski et al., 2016).

2.2.7.2 Further training requirements

EPC assessors must complete a post-graduate course in the field of engineering and energy auditing for thermo-modernization or be a licensed engineer according to the Polish law. The training course or post-graduate study must include 50 hours of training on certification methodology, calculation, regulations, and assessment of buildings on thermal protection, HVAC and lighting systems (Buildings Performance Institute Europe, 2017a). Since 9 March 2015, every qualified expert must be registered in the relevant database of the central register of the energy performance of buildings (Bekierski et al., 2016).

2.2.8 Slovenia

2.2.8.1 Basic education requirements for assessors

A 3-year university degree in technical fields, a minimum of 2 years' experience in building energy efficiency and renewable energy sources in buildings (Zavrl et al., 2016).

2.2.8.2 Further training requirements

Qualified individuals should participate in a one-week training and pass written and oral examinations (Zavrl et al., 2016).

2.2.9 Spain

2.2.9.1 Basic education requirements for assessors

Having an academic degree of engineer, architect or technical vocational training in Spanish FP (Gokarakonda et al., 2020).

2.2.9.2 Further training requirements

No additional training is required (Gokarakonda et al., 2020).

2.2.10 UK

2.2.10.1 Basic education requirements for assessors

No qualifications or prior experience is required to train as an energy assessor.

2.2.10.2 Further training requirements

There are different levels of qualifications for energy assessors based on the type of buildings. In general, the Occupational Standards (NOS) specify the qualifications and skills energy assessors should meet to be accredited to produce regulatory outputs (Delorme and Anne-Marie, 2020).

- For existing domestic buildings: complete a Level 3 Certificate in Domestic Energy Assessment (DEA) and become a member of an approved accreditation scheme. A Domestic Energy Assessor will carry out energy assessments on existing houses, flats, and bungalows. The training for this certificate usually takes around 5 days (Delorme and Anne-Marie, 2020).
- For non-domestic buildings: There are various levels of certification based on the complexity of the building systems as well as whether the building is new, ranging from level 3 for simple buildings to level 5 for the most complex. A level 3 Non-Domestic Energy Assessor (NDEA) diploma holder can carry out assessments on small existing buildings with heating systems less than 100 KW and cooling systems less than 12 KW. A level 4 Non-Domestic Energy Assessor (NDEA) can perform EPC assessments on newly built buildings and large existing buildings with heating systems greater than 100 KW and cooling systems greater than 12 KW. A level 4 diploma is also required if any specialized fixed services such as VAV, fan coils or chilled ceilings are used. A level 3 and 4 training course usually takes around 3-5 days. Level 5 EPC certificates are for the most complex buildings that could have features such as ventilation with enhanced thermal coupling to the structure, automatic blind and vent controls, and atria. Level 5 buildings must be assessed using an approved Dynamic Simulation Modelling (DSM) software (Guilds, 2020).

- All certified energy assessors in the UK must adhere to a mandatory Continuing Professional Development (CPD) policy. The policy states that in order to maintain a valid certification, energy assessor must complete 10 hours Valid CPD per certification strand each year. For any additional strands, the certified assessor must complete an additional 5 hours Valid CPD per additional strand i.e. DEA and NDEA (NDEA LEVEL 3, 4 and DEC's count as one strand (CPD, 2022)).

3 EPC software and general methodology

3.1 EPC software

The section below identifies and references the software and associated methodology adopted by each country.

3.1.1 Austria

In Austria, an official software is not available. However, there are five commercial programs available for EPC calculations: ArchiPHYSIK, AX3000, ecoline, Ecotech Gebäuderechner, GEQ, Grüner GmbH, Gebäudeprofi. These tools use the OIB Guideline 6 methodology for EPC calculation. OIB 2019 is the latest version, however it is possible to select previous versions of the guidelines as well (Fueyo and Herrando, 2022).

All EPC calculation software are validated using an excel tool developed by the Austrian Institute of Construction Engineering (OIB) (Volt et al., 2020).

3.1.2 Bulgaria

In Bulgaria, official software including EAB, EECalc and Shtrakov are used for EPC calculation (Fueyo and Herrando, 2022).

3.1.3 Croatia

The official EPC software is MGIPU Energetski certifikator Energetski certifikator. There are also several other options available on the market (Fueyo and Herrando, 2022).

3.1.4 Denmark

Be18 is the EPC calculation program developed by the Danish Building Research Institute, based on the Danish Building Regulations (BR15). Other tools such as Energy10 are also available which must use the calculation engine of the Be18 (Thomsen et al., 2021).

3.1.5 Greece

Calculations are performed with the use of the official national software (TEEKENAK), available (at low cost) from the Technical Chamber of Greece and integrated in the EPC registry web platform. This calculation engine is based on the EPA-NR tool open data format (XML) and is developed by the National Observatory of Athens (Fueyo and Herrando, 2022). Other commercial software tools (4MKENAK, Buildingsoft GoEnergy CAD-PRO, Civiltech Energy Certificate CAD, etc.), using the calculation engine of TEE KENAK, are used to reduce the workload for energy inspectors by integrating shading calculations and building drawings (Buildings Performance Institute Europe, 2017b). These can be used but need to be checked and approved by the public authority (Volt et al., 2020) (Fueyo and Herrando, 2022).

3.1.6 Malta

For dwellings, the national calculation tool developed is the 'Energy Performance Rating of Dwellings in Malta' (EPRDM). which is based on an xml file used for both design and asset rating EPCs (Fueyo and Herrando, 2022).

For non-dwelling EPCs, iSBEM software (as developed through the UK method via the Building Research Establishment (BRE)), is used for both design and asset rating EPCs and runs on MS Access (Fueyo and Herrando, 2022).

3.1.7 Poland

There is no official software for EPC calculation in Poland. Various tools including Audytor OZC, ArCADia-TEROMCAD PRO 2020, BuildDesk Energy Certificate are compliant with ISO 13790 and used for EPC calculations (Fueyo and Herrando, 2022, Volt et al., 2020)

3.1.8 Slovenia

There appears to be no official software for EPC calculation in Slovenia. However, commercial software such as KI Energy or URSA are available and used by assessors to perform EPC calculations.

3.1.9 Spain

There are 7 different official software are approved by the central government in Spain. Four of these tools (HULC, SG SAVE, CYPE THERM HE PLUS, TEXTON3D TK-CEEP) use more detailed inputs and are based on calculation engines such as DOE2, BLAST, ESP, SERIRES/SUNCODE, SERIRES, S3PAS, TAS, TRNSYS, ENERGYPLUS. These tools can be used for EPC calculations of new and existing residential and non-residential buildings. Other software including Ce3X, CE3, CERMA are based on a simplified methodology and can only be used for existing buildings. The accuracy of the simplified methodology is determined by comparison with the general reference procedure for the energy rating of buildings HULC (Fueyo and Herrando, 2022, Morsink-Georgali and Fokaides, 2020).

3.1.10 UK

The Standard Assessment Procedure (SAP), developed by BRE, is used for new and some existing domestic buildings and is implemented in approved commercial software such as Stroma and Elmhurst Energy. Reduced Data Standard Assessment Procedure (RdSAP) is used for existing domestic buildings, providing a series of look-up input tables to account for information that might not be available for existing buildings.

The Simplified Building Energy Model (SBEM), also developed by BRE (see Malta notes), for non-domestic buildings is implemented in an official tool called iSBEM. Dynamic simulation can also be used in case of larger non-domestic buildings with complex HVAC systems (Fueyo and Herrando, 2022).

3.2 Is there a simplified (reduced) methodology available for buildings with limited data access?

Simplified (or reduced) methods are defined here as providing additional assumptions (and potentially reduced reliance on real data collection) to allow an EPC to be generated for buildings where some input data is incomplete or unavailable. This might be the case for existing buildings, where access to original plans/drawings is not possible. Among crossCert countries, Spain and UK provide simplified versions of their methodology for certain categories of buildings. In the Spanish methodology, some of the input data can be defaulted or inferred for existing buildings. In the British methodology, a reduced data version of SAP (RdSAP) is used for existing residential buildings when the complete dataset for a SAP calculation is not available, RdSAP has been developed where some of the data items are defaulted or inferred.

3.3 EPC assessment based on calculation (asset rating) or energy consumption (operational rating)

The EPBD allows using calculation or actual energy consumption data for EPC calculation. According to the EPBD's Annex I, "The energy performance of a building shall be determined on the basis of calculated or actual energy use and shall reflect typical energy use for space heating, space cooling, domestic hot

water, ventilation, built-in lighting and other technical building systems.” (EPBD, 2018). This section provides information regarding the approach of each crossCert partner country, based on the survey results as well as the relevant literature.

3.3.1 Austria

The EPC is issued based on calculation for all buildings.

3.3.2 Bulgaria

In Bulgaria, though it is not possible to issue an EPC based on measured data (operational rating), measurements are needed to define the mandatory calculated EPC. The procedure accounts for the measurement-based calibration of the calculated annual energy consumption per service, considering weather normalization for the heating service (Carnero Melero et al., 2022).

3.3.3 Denmark

Buildings can be certified according to calculated or actual consumption. The calculated consumption is based on standard assumptions while the certification based on actual consumption requires an operating record with monthly readings of energy consumption over at least 1 year.

3.3.4 Greece

The EPC methodologies for both residential and non-residential buildings are based on calculations (asset rating).

3.3.5 Malta

The EPC methodologies for both residential and non-residential buildings are based on calculations (asset rating).

3.3.6 Poland

Existing buildings which have gas, electricity or heat meters and where 36 continuous months of utility bills are available can use actual energy use to generate EPCs. For other buildings, calculations are used (Semple and Jenkins, 2020).

3.3.7 Slovenia

For all residential buildings (new and existing) and for new non-residential buildings, EPC is an asset rating, where the calculation methodology defined by the building code PURES is used. Operational rating can only be used for existing non-residential buildings.

3.3.8 Spain

The EPC methodologies for both residential and non-residential buildings are based on calculations (asset rating)..

3.3.9 UK

The EPC is based on an asset rating and therefore it is based on calculation for all building categories in the UK. However, in England, Wales, and Northern Ireland, for buildings occupied by a public authority frequently visited by the public where the total useful floor area of the building exceeds 250m², another a separately calculated Display Energy Certificate (DECs) is required which shows the energy performance of the building based on actual energy consumption as recorded over the last 12 months within the validity period of the DEC (the operational rating). Such public buildings should, if an EPC is already present, display the EPC alongside the DEC. In Scotland, the DEC is only a reporting option for non-domestic buildings (BRE, 2020).

3.4 Site visit

The use of a site visit and in-situ data collection also varies across countries. This is potentially important when understanding the labour required during an energy assessment, the use of real input information, and the replicability of energy assessment methods. The differences below also indicate subtle differences between an energy assessor and an energy/building “surveyor”, with some correlation with the training/education background of that assessor (see Section 2.2)

3.4.1 Austria

A site visit is not obligatory (Gokarakonda, 2020).

3.4.2 Bulgaria

Certifiers must visit the building and perform an energy audit (for existing buildings) and perform visual checks (for new buildings), including an interview with the owner/technical staff. They should also perform measurements on-site and analyse the bills, data on energy (heat, electricity) and water consumption for the last 3 year (Fueyo and Herrando, 2022).

3.4.3 Croatia

Site visit is obligatory for buildings where a total heated floor area over 250 m² is occupied by a public authority and frequently visited by the public, new buildings before issuing a use permit and buildings that are for rent or sale (Stapić et al., 2017).

3.4.4 Denmark

On-site inspection is mandatory for all buildings except for the buildings with the BBR use codes 110 (houses in agricultural property), 120 (detached single-family house) and 130, 131 and 132 (row, chain or semi-detached house), given the building in these categories meets the following criteria (The Danish Energy Agency, 2021):

- The building must have been constructed a maximum of 25 years before the energy label.
- Requirements for energy labeling of the building for new construction have been complied with.
- The heat supply is oil, natural gas, district heating, electricity (including heat pump) or biofuel with a central heating system.

3.4.5 Greece

A site visit by the assessor is obligatory (Gokarakonda, 2020).

3.4.6 Malta

A site visit by the assessor is obligatory (Gokarakonda, 2020).

3.4.7 Poland

While not mandatory, it is recommended to visit the building before an EPC assessment (Gokarakonda, 2020).

3.4.8 Slovenia

Site visits are not obligatory for new buildings and residential buildings. For other buildings it is mandatory to visit the site before an EPC assessment (Gokarakonda, 2020, Fueyo and Herrando, 2022).

3.4.9 Spain

A site visit is mandatory. A technician should visit the building at least once, maximum 3 months before issuing the EPC (Fueyo and Herrando, 2022).

3.4.10 UK

In-person visit by a trained, certified, energy assessor is mandatory (Fueyo and Herrando, 2022).

3.5 Zoning the building based on activity types

An indicator of the calculation approach, and the building input detail required, is the use of zoning in the thermal models used by EPCs. Zoning by activity and/or room area can place extra requirements on the calculation method and the assessor, as well as generating significant differences in energy calculation for given building types modelled across different methods. It is also noticeable that some countries see the need for zoning for non-residential buildings, whilst not requiring it for residential buildings.

3.5.1 Austria

According to the OIB Guideline 6 (OIB, 2019), there are only certain circumstances that require dividing the building into separate zones:

- If less than 80% of the building (gross floor area) is supplied by the same HVAC or domestic hot water system,
- If less than 80% of the building (gross floor area) is supplied by the same lighting system,
- If different requirements must be met for parts of the building (e.g., new building requirements for the attic extension, but only refurbishment requirements for the renovation of the base floors)
- If the balance internal temperature of two adjacent spaces differs by more than 4°C.

3.5.2 Bulgaria

The assessor has the option of dividing the building into different zones.

3.5.3 Denmark

Residential buildings are treated as a single zone. Non-residential buildings can be divided into zones based on temperature setpoints, ventilation requirement, or lighting. In addition, for mixed use buildings, i.e., buildings registered as multiple uses such as office, warehouse, residential, etc. in the Central Register of Buildings and Dwellings (BBR), the residential part is considered as one zone and commercial parts are divided into zones based on criteria mentioned before. Buildings are certificated with mixed use when the building has sections with a different use than the main use, and the section:

- is at least 1,000 m² of the heated floor area,
- or constitutes at least 20% of the total heated floor area in the building.

In these cases, the building is certificated as one building with one EPC but must be divided into zones (The Danish Energy Agency, 2021).

3.5.4 Greece

All buildings can be divided into different zones. Spaces qualifying the following conditions must be considered as separate thermal zones (Technical chamber of Greece, 2012):

- The temperature setpoint differs by more than 4°C from the rest of the building
- Different activities where internal default conditions are different
- Spaces served by different HVAC systems
- Significant heat loss/gains compared to the rest of the building e.g., south facing rooms
- The ventilation system covers less than 80% of the floor area.

3.5.5 Malta

Non-residential buildings are divided into zones based on activity type, HVAC and lighting systems and are entered into iSBEM software accordingly. Residential buildings are considered as a single zone.

3.5.6 Poland

All buildings can be divided into zones.

3.5.7 Slovenia

Non-residential buildings should be divided into zones based on activity type, HVAC, and lighting systems. For residential buildings, the building is considered as one zone for simplifying the calculation.

3.5.8 Spain

The Ce3X software allows the user to divide all types of building into different zones.

3.5.9 UK

Non-residential buildings should be divided into zones based on activity type, HVAC and lighting systems. Residential buildings are treated as a single zone.

3.6 Are the results calibrated against actual energy consumption?

Results of the building model are not calibrated against actual energy consumption data in most of the partner countries. Of the countries studied, and from the information available, only in the Bulgarian methodology is a clear energy consumption calibration stage identified that requires the assessor to change inputs to meet a target consumption. In this case, the EPC results for existing buildings must be calibrated against actual energy consumption data of the past 3 years (Carnero Melero et al., 2022). Also in the Danish method, actual energy consumption is used for a more specific calibration for the inputs relating to lighting and HVAC system parameters (The Danish Energy Agency, 2021).

3.7 Energy consumption included in EPC rating

According to EPBD Annex 1, the energy performance of a building shall “reflect typical energy use for space heating, space cooling, domestic hot water, ventilation, built-in lighting and other technical building systems (technical building system means technical equipment for space heating, space cooling, ventilation, domestic hot water, built-in lighting, building automation and control, on-site electricity generation, or a combination thereof, including those systems using energy from renewable sources, of a building or building unit)” (EPBD, 2018). However, reviewing the methodologies of the partner countries reveals some differences in the energy use considered in the calculation of the energy performance of buildings. While all countries take into account heating, domestic hot water (DHW) and ventilation in their EPC calculation, there are differences in relation to cooling, lighting and electrical equipment usage (with the inclusion, or not, of appliances as a contributor to the energy rating of particular note). This section reviews the energy usage considered in each country’s methodology, with a summary provided in Table 1.

3.7.1 Austria

The assessment calculates energy due to heating (including humidification), hot water supply, cooling, ventilation, lighting (only in non-residential buildings), household power requirements (for residential buildings) or operational power requirements (for non-residential buildings).

3.7.2 Bulgaria

Energy consumption is calculated for heating, cooling, ventilation, hot water supply, lighting, and appliances for all buildings.

3.7.3 Denmark

Energy consumption is calculated for heating, cooling, and ventilation, and hot water supply for all buildings. Lighting energy consumption is included in the calculations for non-residential buildings. For multifamily houses only the lighting in common areas such as common rooms, stairs and corridors is considered, and for single-family houses lighting is not considered in calculations. (The Danish Energy Agency, 2021).

Table 1- Energy uses included in each country methodology

		Heating	Cooling	ventilation	DHW	Lighting	Equipment
Austria	Residential	✓	✓	✓	✓		-
	Non-residential	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Bulgaria	Residential	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
	Non-residential	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Denmark	Residential	✓	✓	✓	✓	only in communal parts of multi-family houses	-
	Non-residential	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	-
Greece	Residential	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	-
	Non-residential	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	-
Malta	Residential	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	-
	Non-residential	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	-
Poland	Residential	✓	✓	✓	✓	-	-
	Non-residential	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	-
Slovenia	Residential	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	-
	Non-residential	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	-
Spain	Residential	✓	✓	✓	✓	-	-
	Non-residential	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	-
UK	Residential	✓	--	✓	✓	✓	-
	Non-residential	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	-

3.7.4 Greece

Energy consumption is calculated for heating, cooling and ventilation, hot water, and lighting for all buildings.

3.7.5 Malta

Energy consumption is calculated for heating, cooling and ventilation, hot water, and lighting for all buildings.

3.7.6 Poland

Energy consumption is calculated for heating, cooling, ventilation, and hot water supply for all buildings. Lighting energy consumption is only considered in non-residential buildings.

3.7.7 Slovenia

Energy consumption is calculated for heating, cooling, ventilation, hot water, and lighting for all buildings (PIS, 2020).

3.7.8 Spain

Energy consumption is calculated for heating, cooling and ventilation, humidity control, and hot water supply. Lighting energy consumption is only considered in non-residential buildings.

3.7.9 UK

For residential buildings, the energy performance rating includes energy used for heating, ventilation, hot water, and lighting. For non-residential, energy consumption for cooling is considered in addition to the mentioned energy uses.

4 Inputs

In calculation-based EPC methodologies, inputs play an important role in the final rating. The input parameters that depend on the users of the building, such as HVAC, lighting and equipment schedules, occupancy profiles and temperature setpoints, are standardized in some EPC methodologies to facilitate comparison between different buildings. In addition, for other inputs such as U-values and HVAC systems' specifications, there are databases available in some methodologies, providing values for commonly used construction types or systems. This section is focused on whether standardized inputs are supplied in partner countries' methodologies and the differences between these standards.

4.1 HVAC systems schedules

Timing and operation of HVAC can be tailored to an activity or building type, or recorded in a more bespoke manner for a specific building. The below section summarises the approach in the different countries.

4.1.1 Austria

ÖNORM B 8110-5 provides default HVAC schedules for different building use-types which are implemented in the EPC software. These schedules must be used in EPC calculations for the certificate to be valid (OIB, 2019).

4.1.2 Bulgaria

There are no standard HVAC schedules available. The assessor collects the information about the HVAC operation times on-site and uses this information as an input in the software.

4.1.3 Denmark

Both natural and mechanical ventilation schedules in single-family residential buildings are assumed to be 24-hrs (always on). For multi-family houses and non-residential buildings, the fraction of the operating time of the building that the ventilation system is on can be specified manually by the assessor in the EPC calculation software (The Danish Energy Agency, 2021).

4.1.4 Greece

Default HVAC schedules are applied automatically by the software based on building/zone use-types (Technical chamber of Greece, 2012).

4.1.5 Malta

For non-residential buildings, default HVAC operation schedules for different activity types (e.g., office, university classroom, office kitchen, etc.) are provided in the iSBEM software.

For residential buildings, the EPRDM software assumes an eight-hour occupancy schedule from 6 AM to 8 AM and 5 PM to 11 PM which applies to the HVAC system.

4.1.6 Poland

There are no default HVAC schedules in the Polish EPC methodology. These schedules can be entered manually based on the assessor's information or using a standard.

4.1.7 Slovenia

For non-residential buildings, the national calculation methodology (PURES 2010) defines the operation schedule according to SIST EN ISO 13790 Annex G unless defined otherwise in the design brief and design documentation. For residential buildings 24hr use (continuous heating) is assumed.

4.1.8 Spain

For non-residential buildings, the HVAC schedules can be defined by the assessor based on the information gathered on-site. In the absence of such information, standard schedules are also provided in legislations that can be used in calculations. Twelve default schedules are available which are defined based on the level of internal heat gains (low, medium or high) and building operation times (8hr, 12hr, 16hr and 24hr). These schedules are applied to the entire building when selected, meaning it's not possible to apply different schedules to different zones.

For residential buildings, operational schedules and setpoints are set out in the Technical Building Code of Spanish legislation, which are included by default in Ce3X. These schedules are:

- 7 AM-11 PM on setpoint temperature and 11 PM-7 AM on setback temperature for the heating season (January to May)
- 3 PM-12 AM and 12 AM- 7 AM on setpoint temperature and 7 AM-15 PM on setback temperature for the cooling season (June to September).

4.1.9 UK

For non-residential buildings, the National Calculation Methodology (NCM) provides HVAC operation schedules for different activity types (e.g., office, university classroom, office kitchen, etc.) which are implemented in the iSBEM software.

For residential buildings, the SAP calculations are based on the fixed schedules. The heating schedule is 7-9 AM and 4 PM-11 PM on weekdays and 7AM-11PM for weekends. For cooling, the calculations are based on a standard cooling pattern of 6 hours/day operation, for the months of June, July and August (though cooling calculations are indicative and not part of the EPC rating).

4.2 HVAC equipment parameters

Defining equipment by efficiencies, Coefficients of Performance, etc can allow for a degree of standardization for countries where formal databases of products are used. However, some countries place the reliance on assessor judgement for defining these parameters, raising the possibility of inconsistencies in how the performance of HVAC systems are defined within the EPC methodology.

4.2.1 Austria

Technical details about HVAC equipment should be collected by the assessor using manufacturer documents or equipment nameplates. In the absence of such information, default values are provided in the software and can be used.

4.2.2 Bulgaria

There are no default values provided for the HVAC equipment. The assessor collects the information about the HVAC equipment on-site or from the manufacturer's documentation. If such information is not available, the assessor must use devices to measure equipment performance parameters on-site.

4.2.3 Denmark

According to the HB2021, technical details about HVAC equipment should be collected by the assessor using manufacturer documents or equipment nameplates. When such information is not available, a database of default values implemented in the calculation software (based on values provided in the

HB2021 for various types of systems depending on the year of manufacture and system heating/cooling power) can be used (The Danish Energy Agency, 2021).

4.2.4 Greece

The assessor should collect the technical information about the installed HVAC systems from nameplates and manufacturer documents. When this information is not available, minimum required unit efficiencies for heating systems can be calculated based on the system power by the application (Technical chamber of Greece, 2012).

4.2.5 Malta

In absence of manufacturer documents, default values are provided in the software for seasonal heating efficiency (SSEFF) for heating systems and System Seasonal Energy Efficiency Ratio (SEER) for cooling systems based on system type.

For residential buildings, default values aren't available in the software and COP and EER values should be collected from the manufacturer documents or device name plates.

4.2.6 Poland

In the absence of manufacturer documentation for the HVAC equipment, the Polish methodology provides values for average seasonal efficiency of heat generation ($\eta_{H,G}$) and average European SEER (ESSER) values, based on system type, range of system power, and the year of device manufacture (Rozporządzenie Ministra Infrastruktury I Rozwoju, 2015).

4.2.7 Slovenia

Manufacturer's documentations should be used to gather details about the HVAC equipment parameters. There is also a database of HVAC equipment parameters available at the national Eco fund for the HVAC equipment eligible for energy efficiency incentives. In addition, minimum permitted efficiency values for HVAC devices are given in the national building code PURES.

4.2.8 Spain

Technical details about HVAC equipment should be collected by the assessor using manufacturer documents or equipment nameplates during site visits.

Only in cases that installed systems do not meet the necessary setpoint temperatures, e.g. older buildings with no heating system, the Ce3X programme will estimate that the energy demand is covered by supplementary fictitious systems with default parameters.

4.2.9 UK

For non-residential buildings, if actual values from manufacturer documents are not available, iSBEM provides default values for seasonal heating efficiency (SSEFF) and System Seasonal Energy Efficiency Ratio (SEER) for cooling systems based on the type of the system.

For residential buildings, NCM's Product Characteristics Database should be used as the source for all the HVAC systems' parameters relevant to SAP calculations.

4.3 Lighting and electrical equipment power densities and operation schedules

4.3.1 Austria

ÖNORM B 8110-5 provides default lighting and equipment schedules for each category of building use-types, which are implemented in EPC software and must be used in calculations for the certificate to be valid (OIB, 2019).

4.3.2 Bulgaria

Default schedules and power density values are not available for lighting and electrical equipment. The assessor should survey all lighting fixtures and other electricity consumers in the building during a site visit and use electricity bills to calibrate the power density values.

4.3.3 Denmark

For non-residential buildings and common areas of multi-family residential buildings, values for lighting power density should be taken from on-site measurements or building drawings. Also, a database is provided in HB2021 (The Danish Energy Agency, 2021) for lighting power density as well as light level intensity based on zone activity.

4.3.4 Greece

For all building categories, the default heat gain values and schedules from electrical equipment as well as Lighting power densities are taken from the installed fixtures in the building. There are also default values provided in the software applied to the reference building (Technical chamber of Greece, 2012).

4.3.5 Malta

For non-residential buildings, default values of electrical equipment heat gains as well as Lighting standards (illuminance requirements) (BRE, 2012b) are implemented in iSBEM based for zone activity types to facilitate consistent comparison between different buildings. Default operation schedules for zone activities provided in iSBEM are used in calculations for both lighting and equipment usage.

For residential buildings, energy consumption and internal heat gains for lighting is calculated by EPRDM software based on the floor area of the building. The user can only supply the total proportion of low energy lighting for the whole building. Electrical equipment consumption is not included in energy consumption calculation. For internal heat gains, a fixed power density value (W/m²) is assumed in calculations (Abela et al., 2016).

4.3.6 Poland

Lighting energy consumption is only considered in EPC calculation of non-residential buildings. The power density and the usage schedules are selected based on building type (office, school, hospital, retail...) or can be entered manually. Electrical equipment energy consumption is not taken into account in calculations for any type of building, and only the auxiliary energy consumption by pumps and fans in HVAC and domestic hot water systems is considered. For internal heat gain calculations, fixed values are provided for single family houses, multifamily houses, and various non-residential building use-types (Stapić et al., 2017).

4.3.7 Slovenia

For residential buildings, lighting power densities are collected on-site, or the values provided in SIST EN ISO 13790 Annex G are used. For non-residential buildings lighting power densities depend on actual built-in lighting, operational schedules per type of activity in line with the data in design documentation and/or SIST EN ISO 13790 Annex G.

The energy consumption of electrical appliances is not included in the total energy use for residential and non-residential buildings. For heat gains calculations, default heat productions from appliances provided in the SIST EN ISO 13790 Annex G tables are used.

4.3.8 Spain

For residential buildings, energy consumption of lighting systems is not considered in the EPC. However, default heat gain values from lighting and equipment for different times of day (12 AM-7 AM, 7 AM-3 PM, 3 PM-6 PM, 6 PM-7 PM, 7 PM-11 PM, 11 PM-12AM) are used in calculations.

For non-residential, the lighting system energy consumption is calculated from actual data (installed power (W) and average maintained illuminance (lux)). Default values are also provided based on the lighting type. Default lighting schedules are provided in the software and depend on the standardized usage profiles that the user has chosen (low, medium, or high internal heat gains, and 8, 12, 16 or 24 hour-operation). Equipment power densities and usage profiles are chosen from the default values provided in the software, based on standard building usage profiles, i.e., 1.5 W/m², 4.5 W/m² and 7.5 W/m² for low, medium, and high internal gains, respectively.

The energy consumption of electrical appliances is not included in the total energy use for residential and non-residential buildings and is only included in calculation of internal heat gains.

4.3.9 UK

For non-residential buildings, electrical equipment and lighting operation schedules and power densities are provided in iSBEM for different activity types (e.g., office, classroom, kitchen, ...) based on the NCM recommended values (BRE, 2020).

For residential buildings, electrical equipment and lighting power densities are calculated by SAP using the total floor area of the dwelling, taking into account the ratio of low energy lighting outlets to the total number of lighting outlets (BRE, 2012a).

The energy consumption of electrical appliances is not included in the total energy use for residential and non-residential buildings and is only included in calculation of internal heat gains (BRE, 2012a, BRE, 2020).

4.4 Occupancy schedules and densities

Steady-state models, where exact timing of operation of a building or technology is not accounted for directly, may consider occupancy in terms of a total number of hours in a typical day (sometimes distinguishing between week and weekend days); this may be inferred from a specific time period but it is usually the total hours per day that is the key quantity. Dynamic models require more specific inputs of operation, indicating (for example) when a room with a certain activity may be occupied or when a HVAC technology might be in use. This may be achieved from generic templates of activity, or requiring consideration from the assessor. The below information indicates a variation of approaches to this, and for understanding density of that occupancy.

4.4.1 Austria

Default occupancy schedules for each building type is defined in the calculation methodology and software, and must be used in calculation for the EPC certificate to be valid.

4.4.2 Bulgaria

The assessor collects the information about the occupancy schedules on-site and then uses this information as an input in the software.

4.4.3 Denmark

Default values for occupancy schedules are defined for each building type in the official calculation methodology and implemented in the available software. It is mandatory to use these in the calculations for the EPC certification.

4.4.4 Greece

Default values for occupancy densities and schedules are implemented in TEE-KENAK software and applied to the calculation based on the building use-type. These values can't be edited by the user. For residential buildings, the duration of operation is considered by default to be equal to 18 hours per day, 7 days per week (Technical chamber of Greece, 2012).

4.4.5 Malta

For non-residential buildings, standard occupancy schedules for each activity type are provided in the iSBEM software and should be used for consistency purposes.

For residential buildings, EPRDM software assumes the number of building occupants to be proportional to the floor area of the building. Eight hours occupancy assumed by EPRDM is from 6 AM to 8 PM from 5 PM to 11 PM and.

4.4.6 Poland

There are no default occupancy schedules available. The assessor therefore has to apply judgement for the values used for a specific building.

4.4.7 Slovenia

For non-residential buildings, occupancy schedules for each activity type are provided in SIST EN ISO 13790 Annex G unless defined otherwise in the design brief and design documentation.

For residential buildings, it is assumed the building is always occupied.

4.4.8 Spain

For residential buildings, occupancy heat gain amounts and a default schedule are provided in the EPC methodology which is used by Ce3X.

For non-residential buildings, the standard occupancy schedules and the internal heat gains associated in every space of the building are allocated based on one of the 12 standard usage profiles.

4.4.9 UK

For non-residential buildings, occupancy schedules for each activity type are provided in the NCM database which is implemented in the iSBEM software (BRE, 2020).

For residential buildings, SAP considers a standard occupancy and usage pattern. The number of occupants used in the calculations is estimated from floor area by the software (BRE, 2012a).

4.5 Thermal performance characteristics of the building fabric elements, e.g., U-values

Thermal transmittance of materials (i.e., U-values) and related characteristics can be some of the more standardized inputs to EPC calculations, linked to relatively well-known and referenced material performance. However, different countries will have their own databases to populate this information (even for identical materials) and there is still a difference in the onus placed on the assessor for generating these inputs. As noted with other inputs, this can create a challenge when attempting to achieve standardisation within a country, but also consistency and harmonisation across different countries in how EPCs are generated.

4.5.1 Austria

The assessor calculates the U-values based on information collected during site visits or building drawings. There is also a database implemented in the calculation program providing U-values of commonly used construction types.

4.5.2 Bulgaria

The assessor calculates the U-values based on information collected during site visits and through building drawings. Lists of U-values of commonly used construction types are also available for use.

4.5.3 Denmark

Wall construction certificates or building drawings should be used to gather information about the construction of the building to calculate U-values. Also, U-values for commonly used wall, roof and floor constructions are provided in a database in the HB2021 Guidelines and implemented in calculation software. Default U-values and g-values for windows are provided in Annex 4 of the HB2021 handbook, based on the window type. These values are implemented in the calculation software as well (The Danish Energy Agency, 2021).

4.5.4 Greece

The assessor should collect information about the building opaque fabric elements using drawings and on-site visits and calculate the U-values according to the guidelines provided in K.EN.A.K.. A database of U-values for commonly used structures is also provided in the TOTEE-20701-1 guideline (Technical chamber of Greece, 2012) which can be used by the assessor. Thermal properties of glazing should also be collected by the assessor from the manufacturer's certificate. In absence of such documents, typical values are provided in the methodology and can be used in the calculation.

4.5.5 Malta

For new and existing non-residential buildings, the assessor can use the actual U-value of the building fabric element if accurate information can be gathered from building drawings, or they can collect information about the general construction of the building and use the database implemented in iSBEM to choose the closest construction type for opaque surfaces as well as windows and skylights.

For residential buildings, U-values and other properties should be calculated by the assessor and entered in EPRDM software (there is no database in the software). Reference tables and calculation tools for U-values, absorptivity, emissivity, g-values, etc. are available from the national authority responsible for building and construction which can be used by the assessors.

4.5.6 Poland

The Audytor OZC software has a database for U-values of building fabric elements, which is quite outdated. Therefore, actual U-values should be calculated by the assessor using building drawings. In the absence of such information, assessors usually use their previous knowledge and experience. Information about U-value and dimensions for windows and doors should be collected by the assessor using manufacturer documents and site visits. G-values for different glazing types are provided in the calculation software.

4.5.7 Slovenia

For new and existing buildings, the thermal properties for elements of the building envelope (opaque and transparent) should be calculated using building drawings and manufacturers' certificates. If this information is not available, the data is taken from the database of generic thermal characteristics of building materials in the PURES buildings code (i.e., supplement TSG-01-004_2010), which is also included in EPC calculation tools. If the composition of the building envelope is not clear the maximum allowed U value for the period of building construction is assumed for each fabric element.

4.5.8 Spain

For existing buildings (both, residential and non-residential), users can specify the thermal properties for elements of the building envelope if the construction is accurately known. Also, Ce3X can calculate the U-values using its material database if the accurate structure and thicknesses of each layer is known. If such information is not available, the Ce3X software can infer the U-values based on the building sector, climate zone and the building regulations that were in use at the time of construction.

For new buildings (both, residential and non-residential), U-values should be calculated based on the actual construction, using the material database included in Ce3X.

4.5.9 UK

For new and existing non-residential buildings, users can specify the thermal properties for elements of the building envelope if the construction is accurately known. If not, SBEM has an inference procedure which makes use of the NCM Construction and Glazing Databases. The user can supply the building sector (building use), the building regulations that were in use at the time of construction, and a description of the generic type of construction and iSBEM will select the closest matching type of construction and will use the thermal parameters for this construction as the basis for calculation (BRE, 2020).

For new residential buildings, U-values should be calculated based on the actual construction. For existing residential buildings where documentary evidence is not available (except for loft insulation which should be measured wherever possible), RdSAP uses an inference procedure utilising a set of age bands, regions and construction types. Door U-values can be inferred based on age band and where the door opens to. U-values and g-values for windows are provided in a database in RdSAP based on glazing type (single, double, triple, or secondary glazing), installation date and glazing gap (BRE, 2012a).

4.6 Infiltration and Ventilation rate

Air-change rates from infiltration and ventilation are commonly used in a generic way for most EPC methodologies. Linking Infiltration to age of construction and ventilation to activity (or occupancy density) provides a route to consistency across assessors; though it can be seen, as discussed with other inputs, that different countries place a different reliance on assessors (compared to look-up tables and design guides) for inputting this information.

4.6.1 Austria

Default values depending on the building type can be chosen in the software.

4.6.2 Bulgaria

In the “normalized” model, the infiltration rate should be 0.5 ACH and the ventilation rate should be calculated based on the common values for design of the building type. In the “current state” model (which should be “normalized” at the end) the infiltration rate and the ventilation rate can be different. Usually, EPC controlling bodies do not accept calculations with infiltration rates above 0.7 1/h. The mechanical ventilation rate should be measured on-site using a thermo-anemometer. In practice, however, due to the low price of EPC certification, assessors usually skip on-site measurements and use infiltration and ventilation rates based on their own knowledge and experience. These values are then adjusted by calibrating the model against actual energy consumption data.

4.6.3 Denmark

For non-residential buildings and multi-family residential buildings, a database is provided in the HB2021 containing default natural/mechanical ventilation rates based on system type, date of manufacture of the ventilation system and zone activity. For single family residential buildings, default infiltration rates are provided depending on the level of weatherproofing of the building (The Danish Energy Agency, 2021).

4.6.4 Greece

For non-residential buildings, it is assumed that the building is equipped with mechanical ventilation. For residential buildings, it is assumed that the building is naturally ventilated, and the ventilation rate is calculated by the software based on the opening types.

Default ventilation rate values for all building use-types are provided in the EPC methodology and software and must be used in calculations. For natural ventilation, the natural ventilation utilization factor, which indicates the average percentage of time (throughout the year) during which natural ventilation is applied, is calculated from these default values and the duration of the building's operation. Infiltration rates are calculated using the data gathered during site visits or building drawings including the number of chimneys, vents, the number of windows, window types and their position (Technical chamber of Greece, 2012).

4.6.5 Malta

For non-residential buildings, the default air permeability in the iSBEM tool is provided as 10 m³/h.m² at 50 Pa, but the assessor can manually enter a value based on on-site measurements.

Mechanical ventilation rates are provided in a database in iSBEM based on zone activity or the assessor can enter these values manually if the information is available.

For existing residential buildings, the infiltration rate is calculated by the EPRDM software based on building properties such as the number of chimneys, flues, vents, existence of a draught lobby, number of floors in the building and the percentage of the perimeter adjacent to third party walls.

4.6.6 Poland

Infiltration rate should be measured on-site using a pressure test carried out at 50 Pa. If no test is carried out, a default value of 0.2 ACH is used for buildings built after 1995 or buildings that were built earlier, but the windows and balcony doors were replaced after 1995. For other buildings, the default value is 0.3 1/h.

Default ventilation rates are provided based on the building use-type for non-residential buildings. For residential buildings, default ventilation rates are used in calculations based on building age (before or after 1990), building lobby, and ventilation type (Rozporządzenie Ministra Infrastruktury I Rozwoju, 2015).

4.6.7 Slovenia

For the majority of new residential and non-residential buildings, an air pressure test at 50 Pa is performed (due to high performance requirements in case of mechanical ventilation) and the results are used in the energy performance calculation to calculate the infiltration rate. If test results are not available, the minimum requirement for the envelope airtightness from the building code PURES are assumed in the energy calculation.

In case of natural ventilation, the ventilation rate is calculated depending on the activity type in the living or working space and the operation schedule. For residential buildings the minimum ventilation rate to be used in energy calculations is 0.5 1/h.

4.6.8 Spain

Ventilation rates for new and existing buildings are extracted from the current regulation CTE-HS3 which sets out minimum air flow rates to occupied spaces.

Ce3X software calculates the infiltration rate according to the UNE-EN 15242 standard, using the air permeability of the windows and a fixed permeability value for walls and roofs, which is 16 m³/hm²-100 Pa for new buildings and 29 m³/hm²-100 Pa for existing buildings.

4.6.9 UK

For existing non-residential buildings, with a total floor area of less than 500m², the air permeability is taken as 15 m³/h.m² at 50 Pa. Or it can be inferred based on the total floor area of the building and the regulations that were in use at the time the building was constructed. The mechanical ventilation rate values for non-residential buildings are provided in the NCM Activity Database for each type of activity. This database is implemented in iSBEM (BRE, 2020).

For new residential and non-residential buildings, an air pressure test is performed to calculate air permeability at 50 Pa (in m³/h.m²) which will be used by iSBEM to calculate the infiltration rate (BRE, 2020, BRE, 2012a).

For existing residential buildings, the infiltration rate can be assessed either from pressurisation test or, in the absence of a pressure test, the SAP algorithm calculates the infiltration rate based on the number of chimneys, flues and extract fans, age band, walls and ground floor construction type, draught lobby existence, type of dwelling, percentage of draught proofed windows and doors, and the number of stories. Ventilation rates for chimneys, flues, fans and passive vents, flueless gas fires and passive stack ventilators are given in the SAP methodology guideline and are implemented in commercial SAP software packages (BRE, 2012a).

For mechanical ventilation, the ventilation rate is assumed to be 20 m³/h for positive input ventilation. For mechanical extract ventilation and balanced whole house mechanical ventilation, a throughput of 0.5 air changes per hour through the mechanical system is the basis for calculations (BRE, 2012a).

4.7 Temperature setpoints

Due to the cultural differences in adapting to temperatures in buildings (for winter and summer), it is unsurprising to see differences in temperature setpoints across different countries. It is generally true that such setpoints are dealt with in quite a static way; it is usually assumed that the stated setpoint is appropriate throughout an entire period of operation, regardless of season. There are also differences between how temperature is linked, or not, to activity.

4.7.1 Austria

Default temperature setpoints are provided for every building use-type in the OIB Guideline 6. For residential buildings, the current OIB guideline defines the setpoint temperature as 22°C. However, the 2011 guideline which specifies the setpoint to be 20°C is used in the cross-testing to facilitate better comparison to other countries' EPC methodologies.

4.7.2 Bulgaria

There are no default temperature setpoints provided in the regulations. However, temperatures for thermal comfort required in some building types such as offices are provided in an ordinance and used in calculations. For other building types, design norms are used by assessors in calculations.

4.7.3 Denmark

The default temperature setpoint is 20°C. However, this value is adjusted according to the tables provided in HB2021 based on the type of controls used in the assessed building (The Danish Energy Agency, 2021).

4.7.4 Greece

Default temperature setpoints based on building use-type are defined within the software and applied to the model automatically. For residential buildings, the heating setpoint is 20°C and the cooling setpoint is 26°C (Technical chamber of Greece, 2012).

4.7.5 Malta

For non-residential buildings, the heating and cooling setpoints for different activity types are provided in the iSBEM software database. For residential buildings, the default setpoint is 19.2°C for heating and 26.4°C for cooling.

4.7.6 Poland

Temperature setpoints are selected based on the activity type in each zone:

5°C - not intended for human occupancy, industrial

8°C - for temporary occupancy less than 1 hour, where the occupants are moving around and wearing outer garments.

12°C - intended for permanent occupancy by occupants wearing outer garments or performing physical activity

16°C - intended for people wearing outer garments while sitting and standing

20°C - intended for permanent occupancy by people without outer garments (living spaces, offices)

24°C - intended for human use without clothing (bathrooms)

The cooling setpoint is usually 26°C.

4.7.7 Slovenia

For residential buildings, the default temperature setpoint is 20°C for heating and 26°C for cooling, respectively.

For non-residential buildings, the heating and cooling setpoints depend on activity types and are provided in the design brief and/or design documentation, alternatively the setpoints provided in SIST EN ISO 13790 Annex G are used in calculations.

4.7.8 Spain

For residential buildings during the cooling season (June to September), the setpoint temperature is 25°C and the setback temperature is 27°C. During the heating season, the setpoint temperature is 20°C and the setback temperature is 17°C.

For non-residential buildings the setpoint temperature is 25°C during the cooling season (June to September) and 20°C during the heating season.

4.7.9 UK

For non-residential buildings, the heating and cooling setpoints for different activity types are provided in the NCM database which is implemented in iSBEM. For residential buildings, the setpoint is assumed as 21°C for heating and 24°C for cooling (BRE, 2012a).

5 Conclusions

There are several approaches observed in the EPC methodologies of the crossCert partner countries, all of which can fit in a spectrum between a highly standardized approach and a largely tailored one. Table 2 provides a summary of the review conducted in this report, highlighting the similarities between country methodologies in each comparison criteria.

Given the comparative purpose of an EPC, most partner countries' approaches are closer to the standardized end of the spectrum with the exception of Bulgaria, which uses a tailored approach. In the Bulgarian methodology, default values for the inputs are not provided by the methodology, and the assessor uses their experience or actual data collected on site to fill in such inputs. While the performance gap (between actual building and calculation results) might be lower due to this approach, such an approach makes EPC rating comparison between buildings a fundamentally different exercise, where assessors could provide different inputs to the calculation software resulting in different ratings for a given building. Poland and Slovenia also use approaches with some inputs tailored to each building and provide the assessor with a higher degree of freedom in terms of the inputs of EPC calculation. Other countries seem to follow a more standardised approach, with single values or ranges of values provided for each parameter. It should be noted, however that the degree of standardisation should be considered within specific categories, not just across the whole assessment approach. It is not necessarily the case that a country using a high degree of standardisation for one parameter will adopt the same approach for other parameters.

Comparison between the education requirements for EPC assessors in the crossCert countries shows the UK and Denmark have less strict conditions compared to other countries, while Bulgaria and Croatia have the highest level of education and experience requirements, which is to be expected since the Bulgarian method relies more on the assessor's knowledge and their data collection skills. However, there seems to be no relationship between the level of education requirement and how streamlined the country's approach is for other countries.

While this report has tried to overview some important aspects of the EPC methodologies, more research is required in the future stages of the crossCert project to clarify the reasons behind the differences in results, as well as the overall procedures taking place in the cross-testing phase.

Table 2- Comparison of inputs for partner countries methodologies

	HVAC schedules	HVAC specification	Lighting and equipment schedules	Occupancy	Construction thermal parameters	Ventilation rates	Infiltration rate	Setpoints	Basic education	Asset/operational rating
Austria	Default based on building type	Default values available	Default values	Default values	Database available	Database available	Default values available	Fixed	Engineers, architects or some technical professionals	Asset rating
Bulgaria	Assessor	Actual values	Assessor	Assessor	Database available	Measurement/assessor's knowledge	Measurement/assessor's knowledge	Assessor	Technical education with 6 years' experience, university degree with 2-3 years' experience	Asset rating
Denmark	Assessor	Default values available	Default values	-	Database available	Database available	Default values available	Depends on use type/activity level/control	EOF level 4 technical education (diverse backgrounds)	Both
Greece	Default based on zone activity type		Default values	Default values	Database available	Database available	Default values available	Depends on use type/activity level/control	Architects and engineers	Asset rating
Malta	Default based on zone activity type	Default values available for some building categories	Default values	Default values	Database available/inference based	Database available	Default values available	Depends on use type/activity level/control	Architecture, civil engineering, mechanical or electrical engineering	Asset rating
Poland	Assessor	Default values available	Default values or assessor	Assessor	Database available but outdated	Database available	Default values available	Depends on use type/activity level/control	Engineers	Both
Slovenia	Default based on zone activity type	Actual values	Default values	Default values or assessor	Database available	Database available	Measurement/assessor's knowledge	Depends on use type/activity level/control	University degree in a technical subject+ 2 years' experience	Both
Spain	Default based on building type	Actual values	Default values	Default values	Database available/inference based	Database available	Default values available	Fixed	Engineers, architects, professionals with technical vocational training	Asset rating
UK	Default based on zone activity type	Default values available for some building categories	Default values	Default values	Database available/inference based	Database available	Default values available for some buildings	Depends on use type/activity level/control	Diverse backgrounds	Asset rating

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7 Annexes

ANNEX A: Survey questionnaire

1. Are the input data for the following parameters available in the form of a database (within the software or as separate guidelines)? If the answer to any of the following questions is no, please mention how these inputs are collected.
 - 1.1. HVAC systems schedules.
 - 1.2. HVAC equipment parameters.
 - 1.3. Lighting and electrical equipment power densities and operation schedules.
 - 1.4. Occupancy schedules and densities.
 - 1.5. Thermal performance characteristics of the building fabric elements, e.g., U-values.
 - 1.6. Infiltration and Ventilation rate.
2. What are the main categories of buildings?
3. Are there defined temperature setpoints for different building categories/zones?
4. Is there a simplified (reduced) methodology available for buildings with limited data access?
5. Can you divide the building into zones based on activity types in the software?
6. Are the results calibrated against actual energy consumption?
7. Is the methodology based on calculation (asset rating) or energy consumption (operational rating)?
8. What ratings are included in the EPC and how are they calculated?